

THE IMPORTANCE OF INVOLVEMENT OF PRISONERS IN LABOR IN JAILS**Huseynov Tofiq,***The lecturer of the chair "Legal studies"
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One of the most important issues is the involvement of the prisoners in labor in jails and the improvement of their professional skills. A number of state programs have been developed and directed to the implementation of the involvement in labor and vocational training of the able-bodied prisoners in the prisons of Penitentiary Service. Involvement of prisoners in labor, as a type of correctional means, occupies one of the important places in their correction. In the presented material, the legal basis of involvement of the convict in labor and education was analyzed.

Keywords: penitentiary, prisoner, contractor, standard, emergency, public benefit, accounting, post-Soviet, convict

During the Soviet Union, convict labor was widely used. At that time, penal institutions were called Correctional Labor Institutions. Involvement of prisoners in labor was considered one of the most important conditions of the reformation process. However, in those years, the main purpose of convict labor was to ensure the development of important parts of the national economy by using cheap labor. During the Soviet era, the penal system effectively used the labor of convicts to build large constructions, as well as the use of convict labor in transport and other communication-related constructions, creating conditions for the implementation of important economic tasks. At that time, the mass unemployment prevailing in the post-Soviet countries did not escape penitentiary institutions either. Thus, in those countries, including Azerbaijan, the involvement of prisoners in labor has remained an important problem. However, the involvement of convicts in labor would enable these people to engage in socially useful work, as well as their reformation and earning in exchange for their work [1].

When labor of prisoners is used in penitentiary institutions, compliance with the rules of labor protection and safety equipment was considered an important condition.

A basic legislative framework has been created for labor involvement of prisoners in Azerbaijan's penitentiary system. At the moment, the necessary task in front of each of the convicts is to provide them with a job according to their professional abilities, including their skills. Providing employment to prisoners does not mean that production enterprises should be established in prisons [3].

It is true that even if this is considered one of the important conditions, the main goal should be reform-oriented. That is, this process should be implemented in a complex way. Special skills of prisoners should be taken into account in penal institutions, their professional habits should be increased and they should be directed to vocational training. So, if the prisoner is involved in labor while serving his sentence, if he studies in any specialty, then the prisoner is preparing himself

for returning to society. In this case, the process of reintegration and resocialization of prisoners becomes easier [2].

Thus, each prisoner is recruited to work in other production facilities in the places and jobs determined by the management of the penal institution. Prisoners can engage in self-employment in the penitentiary institution with the consent of the management [9].

The number of prisoners involved in household and economic work in penal institutions cannot exceed ten percent of the total number of prisoners who are supposed to serve their sentences in the institution. Prisoners must be involved in labor activities and fulfill their obligations honestly. The administration of the penitentiary institution should take into account the age, health, sex, working capacity, and, if possible, the qualifications of the prisoners, and involve them in useful work. Convicts are involved in economic and domestic work, as well as other work. They cannot be involved in unauthorized activities. The list of prohibited activities is determined by the Internal Disciplinary Rules of penal institutions.

New equipment intended for small-scale production (mainly for the production of plastic windows, furniture and doors) has been purchased in many Penitentiaries.

Article 35 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan states that labor is the basis of individual and social well-being. Compulsory labor, with conditions and terms stipulated by the court decision, is allowed in cases where citizens are required to do the work according to the requirements of the law. Everyone has the right to work in safe conditions and to be paid for their work.

According to official statistics, 29.9 percent of prisoners are involved in labor. However, the indicated number does not reflect the truth. So, according to another estimate, only 5.7 percent of convicts currently work in the field of production. Prisoners working in the specified area primarily produce clothing, bedding and household items necessary for their normal living conditions, as well as tailoring, iron products, furniture,

reinforced concrete poles, and various souvenirs based on the given orders. 6.23 percent of the prisoners are involved in household and economic work [8].

The norms accepted at the international level, which the Republic supports or accepts, also consider the employment of convicts kept in prisons as a positive thing. The "Minimum Standard Rules of Conduct for Prisoners" adopted by the United Nations includes the following standards regarding the involvement of prisoners in labor relations [8]:

- Prisoners' labor should not make them suffer;
- All convicts are obliged to work according to their mental and physical abilities with the appointment of a doctor;
- Prisoners should be assigned useful tasks during the day according to the normal working day;
- Obligations imposed on the prisoners, that is, the work should be useful for the future as much as possible. So, they should be able to continue those jobs even after their release. This should create conditions for them to acquire any qualification;
- Prisoners should inculcate the benefit of useful professions to other skilled prisoners;

The Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe at its 404th meeting dated February 12, 1987, approved by its recommendation No. R (87) 3, set the following requirements regarding labor activity in the "European Penitentiary Regulations" [7]:

- Labor relations in prisons should be viewed as a positive element of the internal regime and should never be used as a form of punishment.
- The head of the penal institution should try to create conditions for the prisoners as much as possible related to the development of socially useful work.
- The nature of the work offered to prisoners should enable them to maintain and improve their earning capacity after release.
- Discrimination on the basis of gender should not be allowed when submitting a job.
- Convicts, mainly young convicts, should be offered work that can be productive and includes elements of professional training.
- If possible, prisoners can choose and carry out the appropriate specialization in accordance with the internal disciplinary rules of the institution.
- In order to prepare the prisoners for a normal life, their obligations should correspond to the obligations and work of a normal life.
- Although the rules for obtaining financial income from the work of prisoners in penal institutions are useful from the point of view of alignment with standards, as well as the efficiency and improvement of the quality of the intended profession, the interests of prisoners should not be subordinated to this goal.
- Work assigned to prisoners is presented by the management of the penitentiary institution or by an independent private contractor, inside or outside the confines of the penitentiary.
- In any case, convicts should receive a fair wage for the work they do.
- Prisoners should have the opportunity to use a part of their wages to buy things for their personal

needs in an authorized manner and to allocate the rest to their families.

- Convicts should be encouraged to save a portion of their earned wages to be given to them upon release.
- Health protection of prisoners as well as labor safety measures should not be stricter than the measures applied to free workers.

The purpose of involvement of prisoners in labor relations does not mean to punish them. It is specified in the Code that men over sixty years old, women over fifty-five years old, first and second group disabled, prisoners with limited health opportunities under the age of 18, female prisoners whose pregnancy period is more than four months or who have children in orphanages operating within the institution are on the basis of volunteering are involved in work. As for juvenile convicts, they are employed in accordance with the requirements of the legislation on labor relations [6].

Thus, the use of convicts' labor, the list of prohibited jobs and duties is regulated by the Internal Disciplinary Rules of the prisons. The work assigned to prisoners should not be an obstacle to their reformation. The duration of working time, protection and industrial sanitation rules are implemented in accordance with the labor legislation [4].

It is stated in the Penal Code of the Republic of Azerbaijan that convicts have the right to stop their work. Regardless of the nature of the work they do, the amount of salary should not be less than the minimum amount established by law [10].

The norm of working time is to be implemented proportionally to the time worked or depending on the production. The rules for payment of wages of persons (convicts) sentenced to imprisonment for a certain period of time and life imprisonment are determined by the relevant executive authority.

According to the terms of the Legislation on the Execution of Sentences, the period of working time assigned to convicts is carried out in accordance with the Labor Code. This means that the weekly working time of prisoners is set at 40 hours. However, "Considering the nature of the work performed by the prisoners, the specific accounting of the work period is allowed, excluding educational institutions. During the accounting period, the duration of working time should not exceed the duration of daily working time established by law.

Involvement of prisoners in socially useful work is one of the factors that play a major role in the process of their reformation and adaptation to society. Involvement in social work is recognized as one of the basic rights of convicts and is reflected in Article 10.2.2 of the Code of Execution of Sentences of the Republic of Azerbaijan [5].

As specified in the legislation, convicts are directed to engage in labor activities in specified places. At this time, their individual skills, age, gender, health, working abilities and qualifications are taken into account. They can engage in self-employment in accordance with the relevant permit. Positive behavior of prisoners is always taken into account in prisons. This enables them to obtain a number of privileged rights. The main goal here should be their direct adaptation to society.

Convicts should not be involved in life-threatening work. Prisoners are given days off. At this time, according to the legislation, they are not involved in other work, that is, they are exempted from all work according to the requirements of the law. Depending on the nature of the work they do, the time they are involved in paid work is included in the total length of service. This is positively evaluated when they get the right to pension in the future. Prisoners are entitled to paid leave. Female convicts are exempted from all work for the period prescribed by law due to childbirth and pregnancy. The essence of all analyzed processes leads to the fact that it is aimed only at the reformation of convicts. Taking all necessary steps for the formation of a healthy society is a responsibility of the state [5].

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